

Chronically Depressed Suicidal

[Name of the Writer]

[Name of the Institution]

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Introduction

People commit suicide when they are completely hopeless and are not able to find any solution to their problems. Suicide is the tenth most common cause of death in United States. Suicide is related to severe substance abuse or alcohol, depression or any major life event (NLM, 2014). Numerous scholars view suicide from ethical and moral perspectives. They consider suicide as the tragic event, which has a strong emotional repercussion. According to the given scenario, one of my good friends is suffering from severe depression and often shows suicidal tendencies. She confides that one day she will commit suicide. She is suffering from depression since past twenty-five years. This essay will present the argument based on the ethical theory of suicide by Immanuel Kant regarding the scenario presented.

Suicide: Immanuel Kant

According to the theory presented by Kant, he believes that killing one self, when life bodes ill is wrong. Kant explained the term in one of the most unqualified ways; he stated that majority of people look suicide as carrion. Furthermore, he explained that if person attempts the suicide and survives, they have discarded their humanity. He believed that man is God's property and he/she has no right to dispose their life. Kant has also presented number of secular arguments of committing suicide. It suggests that suicide is considered as a degrading and abasing of humanity (Brassington, 2006).

In the context to the given scenario, her decision of committing suicide is morally wrong. As Kant stated that treating an individual as a thing is like debasing humanity. If one dominates

the other, so he/she surely under the pressure do what others want them to do (Cholbi, 2000).

The argument of Kant is completely based on undeniable fact. If an individual commit suicide, he/she can no longer perform any kind of moral act. In the context to the given scenario, her decision of committing suicide is morally wrong. Kant presented the complex and rich ideas in his ethical theory of suicide. He proposed two objections in relevance to suicide, which include that there is the self-contradiction in practice of suicide and when the person kills themselves, one use themselves merely as means. The argument is presented for self-contradiction of suicide in both the moral and ethical values.

According his moral standards, prohibition against the suicide is one of the major duties of human beings towards themselves. The argument presented by him lack his characteristics systematically and rigor. There is the lack of authoritative Kantian approach towards suicide, which is considered as the implausible and extreme position. It is witness that suicide is not always wrong in every circumstance, however, it is among the gravest moral wrong. The three distinct lines of argument presented by Kant against the suicide includes, first if from the lecture on ethics, it stated that suicide play a major part in violating the divine will, willing for one's own deaths, usurps the God's right to decide the period of our existence (Edwards, 2007). As we are God's property, we cannot end our lives according to our will. The second argument is suicide is highly incompatible with the system, in relevance to willed ends with the system of nature. So an adage to commit the suicide could not be coherently willed in regards to the universal practical principle. The third argument is developed from the metaphysics of Morals. It holds that suicide is obliterates from the rational will of the world.

According to the scenario presented, being the rational will of the world and the source of moral worth, attempting for suicide is to withdraw from all obligations. This is not the correct

way of getting out of the things. She has been suffering from mental and physical pain from the past twenty-five years. Committing suicide and getting rid of the world make, the person answerable to God, as Kant, stated that no one is allowed to commit suicide, as humans are God's property.

In this scenario, one who believes that life is sacred and in such state of mind believed that killing is morally permissible (Edwards, 2007). However, suicide is morally unacceptable in any case, as Kant explained that it treats humanity as a means. In this case, she is bearing in her mind that for her living is dying; she is perhaps using herself towards the death. This is done in order to attain the tolerable state of affairs until inevitable. According to Kant, suicide is considered as the act of taking one's life out of self-love. He further added that self-love is not possible than suicide is not possible (Brassington, 2006).

According to the scenario, her life situations have led her towards this decision. Somewhere inside she knows that her action is not morally correct, but she justifies herself that she is left with no other option. This is in any case not the justified reason, everyone suffers from the worst conditions in life, but ethically and morally, to end life is not right. Each individual has to justify his/her life in the world. God tested his people by giving hard times, and looks who face them courageously and who gives up so easily. According to given scenario, she should first realize that throughout her life, how many things she is blessed with. Her actions to get rid of the world would create difficult circumstances for other people associated with her. As the theory of Kant explained that world of appearance and things inside individual are equally legendary. If killing is considered as permissible in some circumstances, it cannot contravene. However, people would have never desire for the world that has universalized killing; this would have

made the world coherent. When and if killing is considered wrong, this is due to something, which signifies.

As it has been observed under the given scenario and moral and ethical theory of Kant regarding suicide, that killing oneself in any case is morally not acceptable. The lives of human beings are property of God and one cannot decide to end their life for any reason. In the given scenario, whatever she bears in the past twenty-five years does not mean to commit suicide. She has to think morally that ending one's life is not morally worth.

References

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Appendix

A good friend of yours has suffered from unremitting clinical depression for decades. Sometimes it would cripple her. She has occasionally exhibited suicidal tendencies but never followed through on her thoughts. She confides in you that she is finally committed to ending her life and that she only contacted you because she trusted you to respect her wish and she wanted someone to know. She claims that no amount of argument will dissuade her and that this is the only way to escape her endless torment. Twenty-five years of unremitting depression has convinced her that her plight is unlikely to improve. She is aware that her perspective is pessimistic and limited by her depression but, having operated as a competent person in this condition for so long, she maintains that she is perfectly reasonable in her assessment.